

Production of All Male Nile Tilapia using Terpenoids Extract from Black Cumin Seeds

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Abstract

Tilapia species have been associated with prolific breeding problem, and farmers required effective solution to such problem. Terpenoids have been reported to promote several biological activities in living system. This research was carried out to investigate the effects of crude terpenoids extracted from *Nigella sativa* in solving the prolific breeding problem through the production of all male Nile Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). The crude terpenoids was extracted and quantified from *Nigella sativa* seeds extract according to the standard procedure. Nile Tilapia brood stocks were obtained and allowed to breed and the resulting fries were immediately collected with scoops net which were randomly assigned into four (4) concrete tanks. A group was fed with diet containing no phytoadditive (control diet). During the experiment, fish sexes were determined accordingly. The experimental lasted for four months. The terpenoids percentage yielded from *Nigella sativa* seeds extract was found to be $3.07 \pm 0.12\%$. Results showed no significant association ($P < 0.05$) between the survival rate of fish fed with the treated diets and the control diet. A 100% male was obtained in group fed diet containing 2 ml/kg of terpenoids. This significantly differed ($P < 0.05$) from the control group which has least percentage (56%) of male. The study revealed that terpenoids from *Nigella sativa* seeds can be used in the production of all male Nile tilapia in a safe and environmental friendly approach.

Keywords: All male, Fish, *Nigella sativa*, Nile Tilapia, Terpenoids

1.0 Introduction

After carps, tilapia is the second most farmed food fish worldwide. The world's tilapia production has increased steadily, from 3.1 million tonnes in 2010 to 5.6 million tonnes in 2018, according to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) [1]. As one of the world's main sources of proteins for human consumption, this has emphasized the tilapia industry's substantial contribution to the global economy [1]. The appropriate aquacultural characteristics that contribute to the exponential rise in tilapia production are: (a) ease of breeding in captivity; (b) short production cycle due to rapid growth maturation; (c) acceptability of artificial feeds following yolk-sac absorption; and (d) marketability [2].

The expansion of tilapia production worldwide has also been facilitated by technological advancements, such as the management of early maturity and prolific breeding [3]. Excessive fingerling recruitment in grow-out systems due to prolific breeding leads to overcrowding and resource competition, which in turn produces small-sized, stunted fish with low market value [2]. In order to reduce unintended reproduction in tilapia production systems, several techniques are used, including thermal shock sterilization, all-male culture, high-density culture, cage culture, polyculture with predator fish, and periodic harvesting of fry and fingerlings [4]. Nowadays, it's usual practice to culture exclusively male tilapia individuals since, aside from controlling prolific spawning, males develop bigger and faster than females, which shortens the production cycle [2].

To achieve all-male tilapia populations, various methods are used, including sex-sorting by hand, hormonal sex inversion using androgens, environmental manipulation (e.g., temperature treatment), and genetic/chromosomal manipulation. Hormonal sex reversal using exogenous steroids, particularly 17 α -methyl testosterone (MT), has a high success rate of masculinization [5,6].

MT's high sex inversion potency is linked to the hormone's ability to inhibit aromatase activity, inhibiting estrogen manufacture while boosting androgenesis in the differentiating gonads [7]. As a result, MT is the most commonly utilized method for producing entirely male tilapia in culture. However, MT's carcinogenicity and the related negative impacts on human health and aquatic ecosystems continue to cause public concern [8, 9]. Prolonged exposure to MT during the application procedure can result in hepatotoxicity and fetal toxicity. As a result, MT poses a health risk to hatchery workers involved in tilapia seed production [4].

However, according to Ong et al. [10], only 10% of the hormone in the food is utilized for sex inversion. As a result, under closed settings, chemical deposits form as leachates from uneaten food or as dynamic metabolites released by treated fish. Hormonal residues are made easier to accumulate by MT's hydrophobic nature, which allows it to adsorb onto sediments quickly [8]. The endocrine and regeneration systems of nontarget aquatic life forms may be disturbed by the leakage of MT and its metabolites into the oceanic climate from uneaten or unmetabolized food [11, 12, 13]. Additionally, due to security concerns, buyers do not immediately acknowledge fish that have been treated with synthetic materials [14].

Phytochemicals are a broad class of plant-derived molecules found in fruits, vegetables, legumes, grains, and plant-based drinks like tea and wine [15]. Tannins, sugars, alkaloids, terpenoids, flavonoids, steroids, and phenolic compounds, are phytoconstituents that contribute to plant pharmacological actions [16]. They are widely employed in veterinary medicine, agriculture, human therapy, and other scientific studies [15]. Phytochemicals have been shown to improve fish growth, feed consumption, immunostimulation, antistress, and antimicrobial properties (4, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19).

Nigella sativa seeds have been extensively used as treatment for a number of health disorders pertaining to the cardiovascular system, digestive tract, immune system support, respiratory system, kidney and liver functions, as well as for overall wellbeing [20]. *Nigella sativa* seeds are widely used in aquaculture for a wide range of purposes, including enhancing immunity [21, 22]; shelf life of fish [23]; growth of Fish [24,25,26,27,28] and sex reversal of tilapia [29,30,31].

Terpenoids are secondary metabolites found throughout the living world. They include numerous biologically-active compounds with effects that range from mammalian and plant hormones, antibiotics, antiviral and antitumour agents to phytotoxins, insect deterrents and insect pheromones. They form a major component of the ecological and medicinal chemistry metabolome from which a number of useful commercial products have been derived. They are found in a number of folk remedies [32]. The employment of certain phytoconstituents as an alternate way to accelerate development in the shortest amount of time may address human and environmental safety concerns. Consumers will not be supplied fish that have been treated with synthetic chemicals, and farmers will be presented with an alternative way for increasing fish growth based on natural goods. The use of specific phytoconstituent may also stimulate general health in fish leading to stress resistance that may be conferred to higher production and economic gain for the fish farmers. Thus this study focuses on effects of *Nigella sativa* phytoconstituent in Nile Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*).

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Description of the Study Site

This research was conducted at the Fisheries and Hydrobiology Research Unit, Department of Animal and Environmental Biology, Kebbi State University of Science and Technology, Aliero. Aliero is located in Northwestern Nigeria on latitude 11 $^{\circ}$ 3'S, 12.44 $^{\circ}$ N and longitude 36 $^{\circ}$ W, 42 $^{\circ}$ E [33].

2.2 Acquisition and Identification of Experimental Fish

One hundred (100) Nile Tilapia broodstocks were collected Dan Ya'u's Farm, Malala area, Birnin

Kebbi, Kebbi state. The identification was done using the description of ISSG [34]. The fish samples were transported in a 50 L Plastic container to the experimental site. The fish were released by placing the container inside a concrete tank containing water and allowing them to swim out. The broodstocks were allowed to breed (within a month) and, afterwards, the 5day old fry were immediately collected with a scoop net and transferred into the experimental tanks.

2.3 Acquisition, Identification and Preparation of Plant

The dried seeds of *Nigella sativa* were bought from Birnin Kebbi central market. The plant was identified by a taxonomist in the Department of Biological Science, Federal university Birnin Kebbi, with voucher number; FUBK-BIOSCI-156 and authenticated sample was deposited in the herbarium laboratory of the Department. Sample was then transported to the Kebbi State University of Science and Technology Aliero, Department of Animal and Environmental Biology for analysis. Dried seeds of *Nigella sativa* sample were washed with tap water and shade dried for 48hours. Afterwards it was milled into powder by using electric blender (Emel0526). One hundred gram (100g) of powdered *Nigella sativa* seeds was soaked in 500 ml ethanol solution for 48 hours with constant shaking at intervals as described by AOAC [35]. The mixture was filtered using Watman filter paper, and the filtrates was concentrated by drying it in the oven at a temperature of 40°C for 8 hours. The concentrated extract was stored in a clean bottle, labeled and then preserved in the refrigerator prior to use.

2.4. Extraction of terpenoids

The crude terpenoids from the produced extract were extracted following the method described by Kuo et al. [36]. The obtained extract was reconstituted in chloroform using liquid-liquid extraction. The organic layer was collected and dried in a drying oven at 50 degrees Celsius. The residual aqueous layer was extracted twice with new solvent. The organic layer was mixed and dried to calculate the yield of organic fractions. The yield (%) of the fractions was calculated based on the equation below:

$$\text{Yield (\%)} = \frac{\text{weight of extract}}{\text{weight of sample}} \times 100.$$

2.4 Feed Formulations and Preparation of Experimental Diets

Feed ingredients used for the basal diet include; maize and groundnut cake. They were sourced locally within Aliero metropolis. Fish meal (Danish), vitamine premix were purchased from Agro-tech Ibadan, Oyo State.

Both crude extract of *Nigella sativa* and the three highest isolated phytoconstituents were used in preparation of experimental diet. A basal diet of 44% crude protein was prepared. Terpenoids at 1ml, 1.5ml, and 2ml, were added separately to 1 kg each of the basal diet, to give 1ml/kg, 1.5ml/kg, 2ml/kg of the terpenoids. The appropriate quantities of ingredients in each diet was weighed and mixed thoroughly using electric feed mixer (Kenwood). Each diet was further mixed with warm water. The mixed dough was subjected to pelleting using manual feed pelletizer with 1 mm diameter diet. The pelleted feeds were shade dried for one week [31]. A total of 4 experimental diets were prepared and stored until the commencement of the feeding trial. The Table 1 below described the composition of the experimental diet used in this study.

Table 1: Ingredient and protein composition (%) of the experimental diets.

Ingredients	Basal diet (%)	Weight (g)
Fish meal (55% cp)	36	360
Soya Bean Meal (44%CP)	30	300
Wheat bran	10	100
Corn flour	13	130
Palm oil	2	20
Vitamins and Minerals primex	5	50
Salt	1	10
Binder (Cassava flakes)	3	30

2.5 Experimental Design

The experiment was done using 4 experimental tanks (1000 liters, capacity) measuring 1.5m length, 1m width and 1.5m height. Two hundred and twenty (220) fry mixed sex of Nile Tilapia

was randomly distributed into 11 groups (3 groups were fed with diet each containing 3 of the abstracted phytoconstituent at 3 varying inclusion level in triplicate. Furthermore, a group was fed with diet containing *Nigella sativa* seed crude extract at 1.5ml/kg as positive control and another group was fed with 0.0ml/kg). Each experimental group contains 20 Nile Tilapia fry. The experimental diets were allocated to the experimental tanks, in a completely randomized design (CRD) layout. The water for the experiment was sourced from the borehole. The experiment lasted for four months during which fish were fed with the experimental diets containing phytoconstituent, after which the treatments were suspended and fish were fed with formulated control diet (with no extract included) for two months.

2.6 Experimental Fish Management

Experimental fish in each tank were fed 5% body weight during feeding trial period. The daily ration was split into two and fed twice daily at 9:00am, and 5:00pm respectively. The ration was adjusted weekly based on the new weight gained in each experimental tank. The tanks were cleaned, and left over feeds together with faecal residues were siphoned out before feeding. Water level was maintained in tanks, and on weekly base water in the tanks were drained and replaced [31].

2.7 Sex Determination

After the four month treatment, external sexing was done as described by Guerrero Bamisaye et al. [37], the genital papilla located immediately behind the anus was examined. In males, the genital papilla has only one opening (the urinary pore of the urete) through which both milt and urine pass. In females, the eggs exit through a separate oviduct and only urine passes through the urinary pore. Placing a drop of dye (methylene blue or food coloring) on the genital

region helps to highlight the papilla and its openings. The sex of the tilapia fish was also confirmed anatomically by examining their internal reproductive organ. All fish in each treatment were collected and sex was confirmed internally by dissection and gonads were examined using squash method described by Bamisaye et al. [37].

2.8 Data Analysis

Data collected in this study were analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics Version 29 software. Data on production of all male Nile Tilapia were expressed in percentages and presented in Bar chart.

3.0 Results

Crude Terpenoids had the percentage yield of $3.07 \pm 0.12\%$ (Table 2). Survival rates of Nile Tilapia-fed diets containing some crude terpenoids extract at varying concentrations are presented in Table 3. The results showed no significant association ($p < 0.05$) between the survival rate and crude phytochemical extracts. However, it group fed with 2 ml/Kg Terpenoids indicated 95% survival rate on. While least survival rate (85%) was observed in a Nile Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) fed diet containing 1 ml/kg of terpenoids.

The percentage of males, intersex, and females among Nile Tilapia fed diets containing some crude terpenoids extract at varying concentrations is presented in Figure 1. It indicated a dose-dependent significant association ($p < 0.05$). After 120 days of the feeding trail, the highest percentage (100%) of males were obtained in Nile Tilapia fed diet containing 2 ml/kg of terpenoids, followed by Nile Tilapia fed diet containing 1.5 ml/kg and 1 ml/kg of terpenoids with 67% and 65%, respectively. While the control group showed a marginal value of 57% males.

Table 2: Percentage yield of crude terpenoids in *Nigella sativa* seeds extracts.

S/N	Description	Percentage yielded (%)
1.	Terpenoids	3.07 ± 0.12^b

Table 3: Survival Rates of Nile Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) fed diets containing some crude Phytochemical extracts of *N. sativa* at varying concentrations

Treatment Groups	Phytochemical	Number of Stock	Number of Survival	Survival rate (%)
	1 ml/Kg Terpenoids	20.00	17.00	85.00
	1.5 ml/Kg Terpenoids	20.00	18.00	90.00
	2 ml/Kg Terpenoids	20.00	19.00	95.00
	Control	20.00	18.00	90.00
Chi-square Analysis		P-value=0.633, $\chi^2=7.953$		

Figure 1: Percentage of males, and females in different treatment and control groups after 120 days of the experiment

5.1 Discussion

Plant extracts have been demonstrated to affect a range of biological functions in fishes, including immune system function, growth promotion, antistress, and sexual stimulation in fish [38]. Numerous functional bioactive chemicals found in plants, such as steroids, flavonoids, glycosides, essential fatty acids, essential oils, and phenolics, are responsible for these activities [16,18,19]. The current study is an alternative method that uses phytochemicals from *Nigella sativa* seeds to

stimulate all-male production of Nile Tilapia and to enhance growth performance in a simple, efficient, and eco-friendly manner. In this study, Terpenoids which was reported to have androgenic effects were evaluated, and the effects were measured in Nile Tilapia fry. The Study indicated that terpenoids has no toxic effect on the survival of Nile tilapia. This is in accordance with the studied of Öz et al. [39] and Li et al. [40] who reported no toxic effects when *Nigella sativa* seeds extract was used on Tilapia. Also result in

this study proved the study of Adimoelja [41] and Adaikan et al. [42], who presented evidence that plant extracts are not toxic to humans and rabbits, respectively. The current study revealed the possibility of using crude terpenoids extract of *Nigella sativa* in achieving all male tilapia production. The findings revealed and confirmed that some *Nigella sativa* crude phytochemical extracts has androgenic effects at increasing the percentage of males in tilapia species. The findings indicated that with the use of 2 ml/Kg crude Terpenoids, 100% male Nile Tilapia can be produced. This confirm the report of Kareem et al. [18]; Gabriel et al., [16]; Sani et al. [29] and Yousefi et al. [43] who reported that certain phytochemicals are responsible for production of all male in tilapia. Furthermore, 100% all male tilapia production in this study is slightly higher than 97.5% male production obtained by Sadek et al. [31] who used *Tribulus terrestris* powder under control environment. Also higher than the value obtained by Eglal et al. [44] who reported 92.3% male using *Tribulus terrestris* extract and Sani et al. [29] who reported 89.65% using *Nigella sativa* crude extract. Omeje et al. [30] reported that pawpaw seed meal (PSM) fed sexually undifferentiated fry of *O. mossambicus* resulted into 77.8% males. In another research, Ugonna et al. [45] recorded 82.19% masculinization of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) fed diet containing 4.27 g/kg. The highest percentage obtained in this study compare to other reported studies could be due to the used of specific phytochemicals which may have acted as a more potent androgenic agent. The use of specific phytochemicals (terpenoids) with highest percentage of male production is in agreement with the work of Okechukwu and Ekinadose [46] who reported the androgenic activity of both terpenoids. The study further corroborate the report of potential of Stadlander et al. [47]; Omitoyin et al. [48]; Mukherjee et al. [49] Ghosal et al. [50]; who used phytochemicals in plant extracts to induce either masculinization or fertility impairment in Mozambique tilapia, and Nile tilapia been harnessed to control prolific breeding, with positive results.

6.1 Conclusion and Recommendation

The present study revealed that *Nigella sativa* seed terpenoids used in this study had little or no effects on the survival rate of Nile tilapia. The highest number of males (100%) in Tilapia

culture can be obtained using 2 ml/kg of terpenoids diets. Based on the findings in this study, the used of 2 ml/kg of terpenoids of *Nigella sativa*, in the production of all male Nile tilapia is recommended.

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